

PROBLEMS IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGE – WAY OF FORMATION OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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Annotation. The article is about specificity of the modern education — problem teaching. Using different methods of teaching is effective. The information technologies are the methods of problem teaching. Methods of problem teaching are defined. Different explanation on problem teaching are offered..

Keywords: foreign language, problem teaching, insoluble, assimilate, acquire, informative

1 INTRODUCTION

The foundation of problem teaching is a collection of interrelated techniques and tools that offer opportunities for students to creatively participate in newly learned material while it is being assimilated. These tools also help students develop the flexibility to be guided and adapt in ever-changing life situations, as well as the ability to independently acquire knowledge that they need for self-realization.

Therefore, problem teaching is a system of instructional techniques where students learn by working critically to solve issues and complete tasks based on the upkeep of the information they have studied, rather than by learning and keeping knowledge in finished form. The well-known idea is the basis for this concept about development of the personality on the basis of aspiration formation to the self-improvement, belonging to the outstanding Russian thinker A.A.Ukhtomsky. And the way of achievement of the purpose is chosen through formation at children of installations on self-education, self-education, self-control according to G. K.Selevko. The ideas used in work belong to activity and personally, focused training which are propagandized in works E.S Polat, E.I Passova. Any problem originates in a problem situation: having realized the arisen difficulty as insoluble at this level of knowledge, the pupil like desire to find a way out of the created situation by means of thinking, i.e. to accept a problem to the decision. From this point the problem turns for it into the task demanding cognitive activity as the pupil knows for what to speak about what to speak and it isn't known how it is necessary to formulate the thought, what means of communication should be used.

2 MANUSCRIPT REPARATION

The problem situation represents informative difficulty for which overcoming trainees have to acquire new knowledge or make intellectual efforts. Problem situations can be objective (the situation is set by the teacher) and subjective (a psychological state of intellectual difficulty at the solution of the put problem). The problem situation realized and accepted by the trainee to the decision, develops into a problem. The problem with the indication of parameters and conditions of the decision represents a problem task

Problem. (from Greek problem – a task, a task). This understanding by pupils of impossibility to allow difficulties and the contradictions, met to it on occupation in this situation, by means of knowledge available for it and experience.

Problem task. It is an educational problem with the set conditions and, owing to this fact the turned-out limited field of search available to the decision to pupils. Set of such purposefully designed tasks also is urged to provide the main functions of problem training: creative mastering training material and assimilation of experience of creative activity

- to consider specific features of each pupil in a class “Problem teaching at lessons of a foreign language – way of formation of creative activity and informative interests of the personality” The basis of problem teaching is made by set of the interconnected methods and the means providing possibilities of creative participation of new knowledge trained in the course of assimilation, formation at school students of ability flexibly to be guided and adapt in constantly changing life situations, independently to acquire missing knowledge for self-realization. So, problem training is system of methods of training at which pupils gain knowledge not by learning and their storing in finished form, and as a result of cognitive work on the

solution of problems and the problem tasks constructed on the maintenance of the studied material. The well-known idea is the basis for this concept about development of the personality on the basis of aspiration formation to the self-improvement, belonging to the outstanding Russian thinker A.A.Ukhtomsky. And the way of achievement of the purpose is chosen through formation at children of installations on self-education, self-education, self-control according to G.K.Selevko. The ideas used in work belong to personally focused training which are propagandized in works E.S Polat, E.I Passova. Any problem originates in a problem situation: having realized the arisen difficulty as insoluble at this level of knowledge, the pupil like desire to find a way out of the created situation by means of thinking, i.e. to accept a problem to the decision. From this point the problem turns for it into the task demanding cogitative activity as the pupil knows for what to speak about what to speak and it isn't known how it is necessary to formulate the thought, what means of communication should be used.

The problem situation is an educational difficulty that learners must overcome by learning new material or using mental energy. Problem situations can be subjective (a psychological condition of intellectual difficulties at solving the given problem) or objective (the teacher sets the scenario). A difficulty arises when the trainee recognizes and accepts the situation that led to the decision. A task problem is the issue with the decision's parameters and conditions being indicated. (Greek: problema, meaning "a task, a task"). Students' comprehension of the inability to tolerate challenges and inconsistencies in their work environment is based on their experience and the knowledge that is available to them. This understanding by pupils of impossibility to allow difficulties and the contradictions, met to it on occupation in this situation, by means of knowledge available for it and experience. Task with a problem. It's an instructional issue with predetermined parameters, and as a result, the students' decision-making space was ultimately restricted. A series of these carefully crafted challenges is also recommended to offer the primary purposes of issue training: training material for creative mastery and absorption of creative activity experience.

In my opinion, by means of problem training at lessons of foreign language it is possible

- to reveal individual bents of each pupil;
- to learn to observe, investigate, stir up cogitative activity since there are no ready answers to questions in one textbook;
- to learn to listen and hear each other, to respect opinion of the interlocutor;

- to learn to live by the principle: "I don't agree – object, you object – offer, you offer – act";
- to interest pupils in world around knowledge;
- to change a role of the teacher (the teacher – not the controller, and the mentor, the adviser, information source which shares shared responsibility for result)

For the successful solution of training, developing, educational problems of problem training of school students on occupations the following conditions are provided:

- creation of the informative difficulties corresponding to mental abilities of pupils;
- providing school students with set of knowledge of the subject maintenance of a problem situation;
- compliance to specific features, compliance to age interests of pupils.

3 CONCLUSIONS

The purposes of problem teaching – formation at school students of ability flexibly to be guided to adapt in constantly changing life situations, independently to acquire missing knowledge for self-realization.

For achievement of desirable result the following tasks follow from a goal:

The developing ability development independently to find and use necessary information on:

- development of skills of mutually control and self-checking
- development of etiquette norms (speech step and behavior)

The educational improvement of moral qualities of the personality (humanity, patriotism, mutual aid tolerance, cooperation):

- development of language, ethnic and racial tolerance, respect for other cultures
- acquaintance with culture a camp of learned language and their communications with world culture.

Advantage of the analysis of concrete subjects and situations is that on occupations. I have unique opportunity to create the concrete problem situations taken from school, household or family practice. Pupils with special enthusiasm participate in the analysis of a situation and make optimum decisions as subjects are very close and clear and consequently are interesting and actual. For realization of a main objective of the concept and tasks following from it I use active methods and forms of education which are aimed mainly at the development of independent creative thinking.

Here two forms of work with pupils prevail, namely: individual and group as I consider that for this purpose there are objective reasons of the psychological plan.

One love and can think, others can't or don't want, but are ready to do everything that to them will tell. Association of pupils in groups on abilities promotes in the course of the general work to self-training of everyone, development of feeling of mutual aid and responsibility for the general result. But there are also minuses, namely: certain pupils in group not absolutely honestly perform the charged tasks, thereby reducing a collaboration assessment because of what sometimes there are friction, mutual recriminations, etc.

Use of information technologies at lessons creates unique possibility of creation of the natural language environment during the work on the project for independent information search, for enrichment of a lexicon, grammar check. Thus, problem teaching teaches children to get knowledge independently.

In summary it should be noted that problem teaching stimulates personal activity of pupils, and it provides the active relation to knowledge, persistence of pupils, and, certainly positive result in training and education. Pupils become more sociable, are able to prove the point of view, find the way of expression of thoughts and feelings.

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